

.....Question everything.....

What is the Nexus Research Group?

Nexus Research Group

.....Question everything.....

Definitions

Definition #1: A club enables students to learn about what is already known.

Definition #2: A research group makes original findings that contribute to our growing knowledge of the world around us.

.....Question everything.....

High School based research

The Nexus Research Group has a history of producing research publications that meet tertiary post-graduate requirements and stand up to peer review.

It is this feature that differentiates the NRG as being a true scientific research group rather than just another “science club”.

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New Zealand Microbiology Society conferences:

The Isolation and Characterisation of New Zealand Caulobacter Species. (1999)

Light Photomicroscopy Using an Internet Webcam Digital Camera. (1999)

Microbiology Misconceptions in Secondary Schools. (2001) *

The NRG was the reason for the setting up of a new Special Interest Group (SIG) within the NZMS, looking at issues nationally and internationally with regards to the teaching of Microbiology in Secondary Schools.

NRG students are invited back to present at this years 2002 conference in Auckland.

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Associates

Dr Alan Cooper – ancient DNA recovery (Britain)

Dr Alvin Smith – rabbit Calicivirus (USA)

Dr Kim Summers – genetics (Australia)

*Peter Spratt – Royal Society of NZ **

Leone Basher – Ministry of Education (NZ)

Invitrogen (formally Life Technologies) (NZ / USA)

Applied Biosystems – genetic sequencing (NZ / USA)

to name a few...

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Star students...

Microbiology Misconceptions in Secondary Schools
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Abstract
A standard and type of questions used in school Microbiology examination papers as a barometer of the perceptions and understanding of secondary level students have about Microbiology. This is the

Materials and Methods
A survey of secondary schools in the North Island was carried out by means of a questionnaire. The questionnaire was designed to examine the current teaching practices in

Results
Figure 1
Schools identified

